
A REVIEW ON ALCOHOL DETECTION SYSTEM IN VEHICLE CABIN

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ABSTRACT

This system provides a unique method to curb drunken people. The system has an alcohol sensor embedded on the steering of the car. Whenever the driver starts ignition, the sensor measures the content of the alcohol in his breath and automatically switches off the car if he is drunken. In this system the sensor delivers a current with a linear relationship to the alcohol molecules from zero to very high concentration. The output of the sensor is fed to further circuitary. If the measured value reaches the threshold, relay cut off automatically.

The main aim of this embedded application is to detect the alcohol drunken people. We are developing an embedded kit which will be placed in a vehicle. Now, the vehicle will be under the control of the kit. If any drunken person enter in to the vehicle it gives a buzzer sound immediately, and now the car will be under the control of the hardware used. We run the vehicle by using wireless communication i.e. from Control section (acts as transmitter) we are ejecting the control signals, then the vehicle receives (acts as receiver) the signals, according to the signals it will stop the motor. It aims at designing and executing the vehicle controlling using sensor. By using the sensor communication, whenever alcohol is detected using the alcohol detector, signal will pass

KEYWORDS: Alcohol Detection System, Vehicle Controlling System, Accident Prevention System, GPS